

Synthesis and Biological Activity of Novel Indolyimidazolinones

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Indoles¹, imidazolones² and imidazoles³ possess wide spectra of biological activities. These observation prompted us to synthesise fifteen new imidazolinones wherein 2-phenyl-3-aminoindole and azlactone have been combined so as to have molecules of enhanced overall biological activity.

The required 3-amino-2-phenylindole¹ (**1**) was obtained by the nitrosation of 2-phenylindole followed by alkaline dithionite reduction. Reaction of distilled acetic anhydride, aromatic aldehyde with hippuric acid in the presence of sodium acetate produced the azlactone² (**2**). Compound **2** on refluxing with 3-amino-2-phenylindole in the presence of pyridine yielded 1-(2'-phenylindole-3'-yl)-2-phenyl-4-arylidene-5-imidazolinone (**3**).

Compounds **3** were tested for their antibacterial activity against *S. aureus*, *S. pyogenes*, *E. coli* and *B. subtilis*, and antifungal activity against *A. niger* at 50 µg concentration using DMF as solvent by the cup-plate⁶ method. After 24 h of incubation at 37°, the zones of inhibition were measured. Their activity was compared with that displayed by the known antibiotics taken as standard at the same concentration of solvent.

From the screening results, it was evident that on the whole, compounds **3** exhibited moderate activity against different strains of bacteria. Particularly in case of antibacterial activity, some of the compounds showed comparable activity. When tested against *S. aureus*, compound **3a** (zone of inhibition 20 mm) showed activity comparable to that of ampicillin (19 mm). Against *S. pyogenes*, the activities of **3a** (21 mm), **3b** (20 mm) and **3n** (20 mm) were comparable to that of norfloxacin (20 mm). Compounds **3a** (21 mm) and **3l** (20 mm) compared well with the activities of ampicillin (20 mm), norfloxacin (18 mm) and chloramphenicol (19 mm) against *E. coli*. Against *K. arogens*, **3a-o** (20–22 mm) compared with ampicillin (19 mm), and **3b** (18 mm), **3e** (18 mm), **3f** (20 mm) and **3i** (19 mm) compared with chloramphenicol (18 mm) used

as standard drugs. Antifungal activity of compounds **3** showed less activity as compared to standard griseofulvin.

Experimental

All m.ps. were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected: The purity of compounds was checked by tlc. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu DR-1, 435-IR spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on a Hitachi R-1200 spectrometer (60 MHz) using TMS as internal reference.

1-(2'-phenylindole-3'-yl)-2-phenyl-4-arylidene-5-imidazolinone (**3f**): Equimolar amounts of 3-amino-2-phenylindole and [4-(4'-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl)methylene]-2-phenyloxazol-5-one were refluxed in pyridine for 9 h. The resulting mixture was poured on crushed ice containing small amount of HCl (1–2 ml). The solid thus separated was recrystallised from methanol-water (3 : 1), (58%), m.p. 128° (Found : C, 76.68; H, 4.77; N, 8.63. C₃₁H₂₃N₃O₃ requires : C, 76.70; H, 4.74; N, 8.65%); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 500 (OH), 3 300 (NH), 1 725 (C=O), 1 540 (C=N) and 1 315 cm⁻¹ (C-N); δ 3.88 (1H, s, OCH₃), 6.9–7.69 (17H, m, ArH + ArCH=), 8.24 (1H, s, NH) and 9.99 (1H, s, OH).

Similarly, other imidazolinones were prepared : **3a** (R = C₆H₅) (59%), m.p. 147⁰; **b** (R = 2-Cl.C₆H₄) (64%), 198⁰; **c** (R = 4-Cl.C₆H₄) (55%), 135⁰; **d** (R = 2-OH.C₆H₄) (53%), 173⁰; **e** (R = 4-OH.C₆H₄) (60%), 141⁰; **g** (R = 2-OCH₃.C₆H₄) (63%), 130⁰; **h** (R = 4-OCH₃.C₆H₄) (66%), 202⁰; **i** (R = 3,4-(OCH₃)₂.C₆H₄) (66%), 145⁰; **j** (R = C₆H₅CH=CH) (58%), 116⁰; **k** (R = 3-NO₂.C₆H₄) (58%), 185⁰; **l** (R = 4-NO₂.C₆H₄) (56%), 161⁰.

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